

THE PERFORMANCE OF CUDDALORE MINOR PORTS IN TAMIL NADU

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Abstract

The present study product of petroleum Oil Corporation limited. The stake holds is part of Nagarjuna fertilizer and chemical plants to diversify from fertilizer to the oil industry. The remaining stakes in the project are held by petroleum of Minor Port. Cuddalore port infrastructure development works are in progress to convert as a deep water, direct berthing port (Extension of breakwater, construction of wharf capital dredging of the channel) under Sagarmala coastal berth scheme with the financial assistance from government of India . Hence, the researcher conclude that the government of Tamil Nadu established separate fertilizer and petroleum handling berth with competing price in all minor ports and also it need independency for improvement of Cuddalore Minor Ports in Tamil Nadu.

Key Words: Petroleum, Fertilizer,Cargo.

Introduction

Petroleum oil corporation Limited (NOCL) is developing a stated of the crude oil refinery in the Cuddalore in the southern Indian state of Tamil Nadu. Construction of the refinery is being carried out in the two phases. The first phase will have a capacity of 6 MT per annum of crude oil and is a expected to be completed by the end of 2012. An investment of INR 7.2 is being made in the first phase. Cuddalore refinery is part of the Tamil Nadu industrial development corporations plans to set up a crude oil refinery to cater to the growing oil needs of the Indian region. The stake holds 51% project investment in the refinery is part of NFCL Nagarjuna fertilizer chemicals plant to diversify from fertilizer to the oil industry . the remaining stakes in the project are held by Cuddalore port and Fertilizer have a direct relationship with food grain production in Tamil Nadu.

Importance of the Study

Cuddalore port is an open roadsted (anchorage) port situated at the confluence of the rivers uppanar and paravanar in the east coast of Tamil Nadu in the bay of Bengal. Ships anchor at the open sea at the available depth loading and unloading of cargo takes place means of lighters steel Barges. The anchorage has 8-10 m depth available at the distance of 0.5 Nautical Mile. Cuddalore port infrastructure development works are in progress to convert as a deep water, direct berthing port (Extension of breakwater, construction of wharf capital dredging of the channel) under Sagarmala coastal berth scheme with the financial assistance from government of India . The depth available at the port entrance is about is about 2.5 m at low tide time.

According to the Tamil nadu Maritime board, the proposed cargo will be a mix of Bulk like coal, cement, fertilizer as well as clean cargo like container cargo. In addition to the berths the project is aimed at modification in break waters, newer installations for cargo storage and handling dredging and strategies for disposal of dredged spoil.

Selection of the Study Area

Cuddalore is large is a industrial town in the state of Tamil Nadu south India, which has experienced rapid rates of coastal development. The coastal stretch of Cuddalore extends from gandilam estuary in the north to Pichavaram mangroves in the south a total length of 42 km along the bay of Bengal. The Bay of Bengal experience seven tropical cyclones in northeast monsoon (oct trough Dec) and nearly 60 cyclonic surges and severe cyclone surges in past century have been reported in the Cuddalore.

Research Methodology

The study is based on empirical in nature. The secondary data where used extensively for based work and analytical purpose. The data were collected from reputed magazines, journals, government published from Tamil Nadu Maritime Board.

Capacity Expansion project- Cuddalore Port

The port is currently under the management of Tamil Nadu Maritime Board (TNMB). The port has been evaluated to have a good potential for further growth with a location advantage of close to major industry, Thermal power plants, coal, mining and product. A survey indicting the potential opportunity and requirement to handle multipurpose cargo and is strategically located on the south east coast of India to support development activities.

Need for the Study

The existing port has become defund for want of required depth of water spread as the port has lost the depth to silting in the last two years. Hence, dredging has become important even to operate barges to negotiate the permitted cargo in the port.

Existing Infrastructure

The proposed location is already declared as port area and delineated to Cuddalore port government of Tamil Nadu.

Statement of the Problem

The real problem is the delivery of goods without serious delays and increase in the cost of because of legal, administrative customs or technical barriers. The area main issue for all countries, but more acutely felt by landlocked countries and particular developing or remote countries that do not have an access to the sea.

Commodity- wise overseas Cargo Traffic Handled at Select Non- Major Ports in Tamil Nadu Cuddalore

(000, MT)

Year	Petroleum	Deferenc	Percentag	Fertilize	Deferenc	Percentag	Tota
2009-10	188	0	0	224	0	0	412
2010-11	194	-6	3.09	229	-5	2.18	423
2011-12	197	-3	1.52	234	-5	2.13	431

2012-13	212	-15	7.07	236	-2	0.84	448
2013-14	224	-12	5.35	232	4	1.72	456
2014-15	234	-10	4.27	234	-2	0.85	468
2015-16	258	-24	9.30	258	-24	9.30	516
2016-17	283	-25	8.83	287	-29	10	570
2017-18	246	37	15.04	300	-13	4.33	546
2018-19	253	-7	2.76	312	-12	3.84	565
Total	2,289			2546			4,835
Average	228.9			254.6			4,835
Minimum	188			224			412
Maximum	253			312			565
CAGR	9.07			9.6			8.76

Sources: Compiled by the Researcher from Minor Ports Annual Report 2018-19 and State U/T Maritime Boards.

Table 1. Noted the Petroleum of the port was delt during 2009-10 to 2018-19. The petroleum performance was increased from the first eight years i.e., 2009-10 to 2016-17, 188 (000 MT) to 283 (000MT). It was decreased to 246 in 2017-18. Than it was increased 253 in (000 MT) during the study period I.e.2009-10 to 2018-19. The total petroleum handled by the Cuddalore Minor Port was 2,289 MT. The average per year handled was 228.9 MT. During the study period. The minimum petroleum handled was 188 in 2009-10 and maximum petroleum handled by the port was 253 MT in the year 2018-19.

Figure 1. Minor Ports Annual Report, 2009-2019

During the year 2018-19 the import of petroleum was increased. Because of at present, as Tamil Nadu coastal area is in a rapid development stage of new harbor, chemical industries, power plants, oil exploration and other large- scale industries, further assessment of petroleum

hydrocarbons and the various hydrodynamic conditions action in the region. Increase in oil prices can depress the supply of other good because they increase the costs of producing them. In economics terminology in Cuddalore 253 MT in 2018-19.

During the period 2017-18, the Cuddalore Port Petroleum performance is not satisfactory. It was goes to 246 (000 MT). It was decreased, when compared with previous year 2016-17. The performance of Petroleum reduced because of to causes. The price of the key raw material, crude oil, cost of refining, government taxes ad level of consumer demand for the petroleum is not up to the mark for increasing the petroleum performance. Hence, the researcher has suggested that the technology there are substantial opportunities to reduced energy consumption cost- effectively in the petroleum refining industry while maintaining the quality of the products manufactured. Cuddalore minor port import from raw material online importing custom warehousing investing in import.

Stated that the Fertilizer handled by Cuddalore port. The performance of the port was delt during 2009-10 to 2018-19. The performance was increased from the first four year I.e., 2009-10 to 2012-13, 224 (000M.T) to 236 (000 MT). It was increased from 234 (000MT) to 312 MT in 2018-19. The total Fertilizer handled by Cuddalore Minor Port was 2,546 (000 MT). The average per year handled was 254.6 (000 MT) during the study period. The minimum fertilizer handled was 224 in 2009-10 and maximum fertilizer handled by the port was 312(000MT) in the year 2018-19.

Findings

The researcher has found that, the fertilizer prices is increased the import of fertilizer. Hence, increasing from productivity is with the rapid growth of population, urbanization and infrastructural development. Increase fertilizer consumption the government should increase investment in irrigation, agricultural research and development extension services. The government policy should be geared toward availability of fertilizer at an affordable price. Strategies for increasing agricultural productivity will have to focus on using available nutrient and water resources efficiently in Cuddalore 2014-15.

During the period 2013-2014 the Cuddalore port fertilizer performance was not good. It was goes to 232 (000 MT) It was decreased when, compared with 2012-2013 and 2014-15. The performance of fertilizer reduced because of causes in the following reason. Now a day, the professed farmers are wish to cultivate the crops with less or minimum quantum of fertilizer or without fertilizer. They wish to improve to pressure the soil from the chemical inputs. The area an organic compound and a major ingredient in the production of fertilizer to an agricultural heavy economy. The organic farming was because familiar, hence the fertilizer performance was reduced in 2013-14.

Suggestion

The researcher has suggested that the technology there is substantial opportunities to reduced energy. Consumption cost- effectively in the petroleum refining industry while maintaining the quality of the products manufactured. Cuddalore minor port import from raw material online importing custom warehousing investing in import. Suggested that the high use of chemical fertilizer, its going up significantly. The government should be take the step to control this or farmer should be realize the need to use natural fertilizers.

Conclusion

The development of the Minor ports related facilities activities or any other activates requiring sea water usage extra. The development of the automobile gave petroleum a new role as the sources of gasoline petroleum a new role of gasoline and transport facility. The demand of fertilizer product in increased continuously in Tamil nadu. Hence, the researcher conclude that the government of Tamil Nadu established separate fertilizer and petroleum handling berth with competing price in all minor ports and also it need independency for improvement of Cuddalore Minor Ports in Tamil Nadu.

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